

A SURVEY ON FOG COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract : Nowadays an exponential growth in data leads to a new paradigm, called fog computing provides a low latency real-time network access. It is easy to access and process our personal data or business information using cloud computing technology which provides huge cloud storage and a central cloud server but the major impediments are its high latency and security issues. Therefore fog computing technology plays a major role in serving the needs of real-time applications such as AI, IOT, and 5G. This paper describes a model of the three-tier architecture of fog computing and its network links. The exponential growth of multimedia data leads to the use of cloud storage is extremely expensive and not good for latency-sensitive applications. Fog computing facility provides high bandwidth and data mobility. Fogonomics business model is a cost-effective method provides all the cloud capabilities to the end of the computing network but charges only for computational services so that we can save data transport cost as well as processing costs. It improves technology and economics. This research study unveils that the addition of fog to the IOT networks comprehensively increases their capabilities and revenue potential.

Index Terms - Fog computing, Cloud computing, Fogonomics, Data Protection

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays a steep rise in the data usage and storage, explosive growth in the interconnected devices, the increased demand for fast processing machines and the availability of machines in real-time and the need of low-latency communication redirecting the attention of people towards the cloud usage. When user requirements increase more powerful machines needed since the formation of data exceeds the capacity of the local machine. It also challenges the existing cloud framework in terms of privacy, efficacy, and security. With the fast increase of business data in small or medium enterprises, the need of huge storage space led to the use of cloud storage technology and to avoid the bottleneck of storage space, they completely store data in the cloud servers. But the entire processing, computation, and storage within the cloud data centers result in high service latency and network bottleneck.

Therefore a three layer framework is proposed in which a fog server acts as a mediator between a local machine and cloud server. According to the IoT market forecast, the total IoT revenue generated by global commercialization is \$4.8 trillion in 2012 [1]. Based on the statistical report of IoT analytics, 50 billion of devices will be connected to the internet by 2020 [2]. Cloud data centers suffer a lot due to such an increase in the amount of data generated from the IoT applications. Due to its processing and storage cloud data centers produce a huge amount of greenhouse gases as well as poor quality of service. To meet the requirement of latency sensitive applications, a new concept has been introduced as a bridge between the IoT and cloud data centers which termed fog computing. It isn't a replacement for cloud computing rather it extends cloud computing paradigm based on the principle of edge computing.

This newly emerged technology brings the processing to the edge devices which are semi-permanent storage devices results low service latency. The term fog (From cOre to edGe) computing [3] is introduced by Cisco systems, a networking hardware company in 2012. The main idea related to this concept is to serve latency-sensitive applications in a distributed computing paradigm and have the capability of managing billions of requests generated from various IoT, AI, and 5G applications. It ensures the frequent availability of networks and increases data processing speed by moving computing closer to users, anywhere they want. In this work fog computing architecture and its comparative study with cloud computing performance is analyzed.

The main objective of this paper is to present the technology and economics behind the fog computing paradigm. Fogonomics is an emerging business model called fog-as-a-service. The pros and cons of fogonomics are still un-studied but we know that a platform is needed to develop business applications on the edge of network.

The rest of the paper is described as follows: The work done so far in this area is presented in section II. A conceptual model of fog architecture is presented in the third section. Fogonomics and sharing economy are explained in section IV. The section V shows comparative study and section VI is for the explanation of the managerial insights derived from case study. The last section concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

During the last decade scientists discovered a technology for storing large amount of data in the remote server and we termed it as cloud computing. The technology grew faster, is an exiting process and new technology emerged is fog computing. This section explains the study related to fog computing. Fogonomics can be defined as the economics of fog computing which deals with the economic factors affecting the architecture and its operations, economic interactions between service providers and end users and its consequences on end users.

In paper [3], Sarkar et al. point that the performance of fog computing paradigm is far better than traditional cloud computing when the number of time sensitive applications increases. In order to solve cloud computing security problems and privacy issues, H. A. Al Hamid et al. [4] proposed a pairing-based encryption method along with decoy technique. They proposed a fog computing paradigm with different architectural components. In paper [5] the authors highlighted the role of fog computing in the context of internet of things and the importance of fog-cloud interaction. They classified the proposed architecture into two sub-sections:

- 1). Fog abstraction layer: Responsible for managing different fog resources and enables virtualization.
- 2). Fog orchestration layer: Contains an orchestration module for providing routing of packets and fault-tolerance.

They introduced a software agent called foglet to monitor the state of the fog devices in the fog orchestration layer and they also presented the potential benefits of fog computing in terms of efficiency and latency. They proposed high-level description of the architecture and examined key aspects of fog computing.

In paper [6] authors defined the features of fog computing model with regard to latency, mobility, heterogeneity, spatial knowledge. This work also explains the principles and theory that belongs to fog computing. Many motivational examples such as connected vehicles, smart grid, wireless sensor network (WSN) and wireless sensor actuator network (WSAN) etc. are peppered throughout the paper. But they failed to define the orchestration of resources and their management. The authors in paper [7] considered different types computing paradigms along with cloud computing. They investigated a lot, to build a framework for fog computing with high reliability and fault tolerance, by combining reliability requirements of grid computing and cloud computing paradigms with the reliability requirements of WSN and WSAN but not mentioned intra-fog communication. Hong et.al [8] designed a programming model called mobile fog to support large number of applications. This work focuses on the programming model for implementing applications on the middle tier. This mobile fog produces scalability, dynamically. Mobile fog contains various processes to handle workload from a certain geo-spatial region. They focused on right programming model instead of theoretical concepts.

In this paper [9] they try to augment IoT applications with the power of cloud data centers. It is a distributed framework for providing computation, storage and networking services between cloud data centers and IoT. Different examples such as software defined networking, healthcare applications, caching and pre-processing etc. are used to demonstrate the concept of fog computing. They explicate SCALE feature of fog computing paradigm i.e. Security, Cognition, Agility, Latency and Efficiency.

This literature review looked at fog computing (FC) and its architectural details and how fog complements and extends Cloud computing. However, the main focus of most of the works primarily on the principles, & the doctrines of FC and not on the implementation perspective.

III. THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF FC ARCHITECTURE

FC is an extension of cloud computing and it is superior to edge computing. Fog computing paradigm inserts a new layer called layer of fog nodes in the cloud paradigm. The main fog specific features are low latency, optimal resource allocation; fast data access and interoperability etc. can be achieved through the scalable edge micro data centers placed in between the centralized cloud server and the end users. The fog computing architecture is shown in figure-1.

Figure -1: Conceptual Model of FC

The architecture contains three tiers: In tier 1, user to fog server communication takes place through edge gateways. In tier 2, we have to consider the communication within the fog computing devices. Every fog devices must support intra fog-tier communication because it must support mobility of the terminal nodes. The interaction between tier 1 and tier 2 is through edge gateways. In tier 3, the communication between the fog devices and the cloud servers are takes place through fog and cloud gateways. These networking details are shown in figure -2.

Figure-2: Networking Model of FC

IV. FOGONOMICS AND PRICING METHODOLOGY USED

The FC market is driven by the IoT (Internet of Things) applications, machine to machine communication, the need of real time processing, and the raising demand for large number of connected devices etc. MnM reports that, the size of market was USD 22.28 Million in 2017 and It is expected to grow to USD 203.48 Million by 2022 [10].

In cloud computing we can define three types of cloud service business models: IaaS, PaaS and SaaS. IaaS which provides customers get access to the service provider's infrastructure but they use their own applications and platforms. PaaS offering provides a platform or cloud environment for developing their applications. SaaS delivers software applications, customers no need to install software in their local system, pay for using the software without owning the underlying infrastructure [11]. The other business models used are IT-as-a-service and database-as-a- service. In cloud computing reservation-based pricing or technical support-based pricing or fixed pricing etc. are costs more and each components charge separately is a highly complicated pricing structure. Amazon web services offer "Pay-as-you-go" pricing structure [12] and Google platform offers "pay only for what you use" [13].

In fog computing, we need to pay for resources based on usage that is pay for resources according to use over time. The pricing methodology used here is "usage-based pricing" is more optimal because marginal production costs and transactional costs are negligible here. We can call it as "sharing economy", an end-to-end based activity of sharing services that are facilitated by a community of on-line platform [14]. Clients can terminate the services anytime without incurring high costs [15].

A. Sharing Economy

It is an emergent collaborative economical model can be used in fog computing, fostered by the services of computing world specifically from the inception of eBay [16]. It is an incentivizing mechanism used with various fields such as healthcare, education, property and transportation etc. The major advantage is that it offers economic benefits or profit for each one who involved in the activity.

B. Fogonomics

The economics of fog computing is referred as Fogonomics. It deals with economic factors that affecting the design of fog computing architecture, software and limited hardware components such as RAM, hard disks etc. of the fog nodes and economic factors of cloud storage, its hardware and software capabilities. It also includes economic interactions between the service provider and the end users. Without a sustainable business model fog computing cannot be flourished financially. The new business models emerged to blossom fog computing technology are 'fog-as-a-service' and 'sensing-as-a-service'. In the context of AI, 5G and IoT, the global market was \$1.9 trillion in 2013 and it will be \$7.1 trillion in 2020 based on the IDC forecast report using 'sensing-as-a-service' model [17].

Fog computing paradigm consists of following parties: cloud service providers, internet service providers and end users. Therefore, to implement "Pay-as-you-go" pricing policy, we need to divide the entire amount for various resources and distributethatamount of money for different service providers. Even though the unit cost of the resources is higher in public cloud, usage-based pricing policy in the presence of variable demand can bring down the total cost[18]. Hybrid clouds (fog + cloud) can often minimize total costs depending on the performance differentials, workload demand variability and differences in pricing. It is also interesting that a dynamic approach need to be adopted to do pricing to get more revenue and usage, just like what traditional industrialize do in car rental, hotels and airline ticketing [19].

V. COMPARATIVE STUDY

A comparative study is made on cloud, fog and computing based on their features, illustrated in table-1. Based on this comparative study we can conclude that fog computing gets more attention than the cloud computing and the limitations of cloud computing can be handled with this technology.

Table-1: Comparative Study of Cloud and Fog Computing

Sl.No.	Characteristics	Cloud computing	Fog computing
01	Privacy of data	Less privacy	More privacy
02	Security Issues	More	Less
03	Business Agility	Gain business insights less quickly	Gain business insights more quickly
04	Rapid innovation	Less quickly	More quickly
05	Service Latency (Transmission + Processing Latency) [3]	Lesser data transmission speed	Low Latency, good for AI, IOT and 5G applications
06	Operational Cost	High	Less because sensor data are used locally.
07	Power Consumption [3]	Mean power consumption is significantly more	Mean power consumption is significantly less

VI. CASE STUDY AND MANAGERIAL INSIGHTS

Medical big data refers to a set of electronic health records. In telemedicine a real-time two way communication takes place between patient and healthcare provider through audiovisual media and integrated medical devices for the purpose of consulting. Here fog computing plays a major role to provide for data privacy as well as data availability with high network bandwidth. The traditional encryption schemes do not provide enough privacy inside the cloud servers, therefore, the users are not encouraging the use of efficient services provided through the cloud computing. With the help of fog we can implement double authentication mechanism for data security using decoy technique; which not only reduces the latency but also increases high network transport capacity, leads to high demand for the facility.

According to the white paper of cisco fog computing system, time sensitive decision can be made easily and it includes all the data privacy requirements as well as very easily we can develop and deploy fog applications [20]. According to Openfog Consortium, fog computing is a bridge between the cloud and the IoT to address privacy, latency, availability, network bandwidth and operational cost [21].

VII. CONCLUSION

In future, sensor based applications need fast responses along with dynamic workloads. With the addition of fog to the network, customers no need to worry about their limited resources; it saves time, development and maintenance costs. In fogonomics, fog-as-a-service becomes more economical only when dynamic resource allocation and resource pooling is done on time-varying workloads.

This work suggests that we need to consider security challenges not only in fog computing layer but also in the cloud computing layer. Security can be provided for cloud layer by using decoy files at fog computing layer with double authentication mechanism and to provide security at the fog computing layer we can use fog-based region verification algorithm.

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